

A Study on Parent's Predilection Factors on Choosing the colleges for their Wards (Parent's Predilection factors)

Dr. J. Krithika

Sr. Assistant Professor, XIME, Chennai

P. Pooja

II BCom, VITBS, Chennai

Abstract:- This study was conducted with the objective of understanding the parent's predilection factors on choosing the college for their wards. The data was collected from 446 parents from Chennai. The primary data was collected by the research instrument questionnaire and the questionnaire was circulated to the respondents by email. The collected data was edited, coded, tabulated and analysed with the help of statistical tools One way ANOVA and Ranking method. Respondents ranked placement record of the institution as the highest among the given predilection factors, and fee structure was considered the least ranked factor. This study can be expanded to different geographical regions and with more sample size. This would help the colleges to understand about their customer's need and will help them align their focus towards the needs and facilitate a better teaching-learning environment.

Keywords:- Predilection factors, respondents, ANOVA, primary data, colleges.

I. INTRODUCTION

Education is very essential for any individual. In India, the importance to education was there from the Vedic period itself. The world's first University, Takshashila (600BC to 500 AD) was established in India. People from other parts of the world joined this university, learned, and mastered languages, grammar, medicine, dance, music, arts, mathematics, accounts, etc. In India, parents play an important role in selecting the institutions for their ward's education and take utmost care in choosing the right one. Many factors are considered in the selection of the college and generally, collective decisions are taken by the student and their parents. An attempt was made to understand the Predilection factors considered by the parents while choosing the college for their child. The data was collected from 446 parents from Chennai, who recently admitted their ward to the institution of their preference, after analysing the predilection factors.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Dr. P. Jayasubramanian et al (2020) in the research article entitled "A study on factors affecting the choice of parents in selecting schools for kids in Tamil Nadu" states that in the process of choosing a suitable school, parents are spending considerable resources like time, money and efforts. The authors opined that education is a gateway to a good quality of human life itself. They conducted this study intending to examine the attitude of parents on the education of their children and analyse the factors influencing them. The sample size of the study is 240 and utilized statistical tools like

ANOVA, Chi-square, and Ranking tools. The factors taken into consideration are school environment, school performance, advertisements, transport facility, sports, and extracurricular aspects, Fees, and Discipline of the school.

Subaashnii Suppramaniam et al (2019) in the research article entitled "Factors Influencing Parent's Decision while Selecting Schools-private in Chittagong City, Bangladesh" states the objective of this research as examining the factors influencing parent's decision in selecting a private school and the factors taken into consideration are the popularity of the school, quality of the service and it includes parent's education and income level too. This study was carried out in Bangladesh with 4 private school parents. The number of respondents is 110 parents.

Flint, T.A.(1992), conducted his study with 931 samples and studied the influence of different factors on the choice of the college by the parents. Factors considered in the study are institutional characteristics, selectivity, degree offering, proximity to the city, and student proximity to the Institution. To analyse the data, the researcher opted for regression analysis. Results show that family and socioeconomic characteristics got a great influence on choosing colleges by the parents.

Walford, G. (1991) tried to examine the school choice criteria and the results surprisingly indicated that the faculty members and the supportive instructors were not as considered major criteria. These variables were not considered while assessing the quality of the schools.

Villella(1990) conducted a study with 740 university students pursuing their first-year degree courses. This study expresses the positive correction between these two variables namely students' college choice and their expectations of the Institutions.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Descriptive design is adopted to study the predilection factors and describe the respondent's opinion as it is. The data was collected from 446 respondents, who admitted their wards in their first year of college in the last academic year. Both primary and secondary data were collected. The major intention was to understand the parents' behaviour and the criteria for choosing the colleges for their wards. The collected data were edited, coded, tabulated, and analysed with statistical tools. Simple percentage analysis, one-way ANOVA, and Ranking methods were utilized for the study.

IV. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

The profiles of the respondents were analysed according to the objectives of the study. Below tables present the profile of the respondents. Collected secondary data were analysed with statistical tools and interpretation is presented.

Gender Profile of the Respondents: The table indicates the gender profile of the respondents as 66% of them are male and 34 % of them are female

Sr. No.	Gender	Frequency	Percentage
1	Male	293	65.8
2	Female	153	34.2
Total		446	100.0

Table 1: Gender Profile of the Respondents

Hypothesis (H01): There is no difference notable in the perception of the male and female parents towards Predilection factors in choosing the colleges for their wards

Factors in choosing colleges	Fd	Gender		ANOVA	
		Male	Female	F	Sig.
Infrastructure	\bar{x}	3.121	3.111	0.501	0.479
	σ	1.121	1.119		
Location and proximity	\bar{x}	3.324	3.265	6.529	0.011*
	σ	0.996	1.040		
Experienced faculty members	\bar{x}	3.583	3.269	5.193	0.023*
	σ	1.531	1.016		
Existing student's strength	\bar{x}	3.245	3.250	0.001	0.970
	σ	1.144	1.123		
Placement record	\bar{x}	3.813	3.868	0.317	0.573
	σ	1.0113	0.967		
Transportation facilities	\bar{x}	3.061	3.098	0.119	0.731
	σ	1.111	1.021		
Fees Structure	\bar{x}	2.945	3.039	0.666	0.415
	σ	1.172	1.115		
Extracurricular activities	\bar{x}	3.099	3.065	0.080	0.777
	σ	1.193	1.131		
Co-curricular activities	\bar{x}	3.003	2.980	0.038	0.845
	σ	1.206	1.147		
Industrial visits	\bar{x}	3.576	3.644	0.423	0.516
	σ	1.078	0.979		
Guest lectures	\bar{x}	3.580	3.592	0.013	0.908
	σ	1.055	0.972		
Tours	\bar{x}	3.225	3.355	1.319	0.251
	σ	1.174	1.044		
Safety and hygienic campus	\bar{x}	3.218	3.269	0.219	0.640
	σ	1.119	1.054		
Training and development support	\bar{x}	3.600	3.631	0.085	0.771
	σ	1.066	1.052		
The popularity of the college	\bar{x}	3.354	3.309	0.191	0.662
	σ	1.045	1.049		

Table 2: Gender-wise results with regards to perception of the parents towards the predilection factors on choosing a college

The table shows the information collected from the respondents and processed through SPSS. As per mean results, it is found that both male, as well as female respondents, considered the Predilection factors equal when selecting the college for their wards are location and proximity, experienced faculty members, student strength, placement records, Industrial visits, Guest lecturers, tours, safety and hygiene atmosphere, and popularity of the institution. Both male and female respondents have given the same importance to these factors. Their mean values were found to be above neutral opinion 3 except for the variables Infrastructure,

Transportation facilities, fees structure, and extra and co-curricular activities.

Results of ANOVA indicate that there is a notable difference in the opinion of parents belonging to different gender on the factors of location and proximity (f=6.529, p=0.011) and experienced faculty members (f=5.193, p=0.023). Therefore, H0 has been rejected at a five percent level of significance for these two predilection factors.

It is found that there is no difference in the perception of the male and female customers on the other predilection factors in choosing an institution for their wards. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H01) has been accepted at a 5% percent level of significance for these factors.

Occupation Profile of the Respondents: The occupation profile of the respondents is given in below table which shows that more respondents are employee category. About eighteen percent of the respondents are professionals, whereas twelve percent are managing their own business. Very less respondents are from the category of agriculture and households. Around thirty-one percent are from the others category.

Sr. No.	Occupation	Frequency	Percentage
1	Employee	159	35.7
2	Business	053	11.9
3	Profession	078	17.5
4	Agriculture	003	00.7
5	Household	013	02.9
6	Unorganized sector	140	31.2
Total		446	100.0

Table 3: Occupation Profile of the Respondents

Hypothesis (H01): There is no significant difference in the perception of parents with different occupations towards Predilection factors in choosing the colleges for their wards.

Customers Engagement Strategies	fd	Occupation						ANOVA	
		Employee	Business	Profession	Agriculture	Household	Others	F	Sig.
Infrastructure	\bar{x}	3.213	3.301	3.217	2.333	3.000	3.057	0.896	0.484
	σ	1.098	1.011	1.223	1.527	1.414	1.088		
Location and proximity	\bar{x}	3.320	3.415	3.000	2.666	3.384	3.201	1.674	0.139
	σ	1.002	0.949	1.069	1.154	0.767	1.036		
Experienced faculty members	\bar{x}	3.572	3.528	3.474	2.666	3.538	3.359	0.573	0.721
	σ	1.850	1.084	1.101	1.527	0.877	0.992		
Existing student's strength	\bar{x}	3.245	3.528	3.166	2.666	3.384	3.187	1.004	0.415
	σ	1.205	1.048	1.199	1.527	1.192	1.025		
Placement record	\bar{x}	3.779	3.773	3.935	2.333	3.923	3.877	1.747	0.123
	σ	1.088	0.933	0.944	1.527	0.862	0.920		
Transportation facilities	\bar{x}	3.050	3.000	3.102	2.000	3.307	3.115	0.829	0.530
	σ	1.123	1.074	1.123	1.000	0.947	1.022		
Fees Structure	\bar{x}	2.874	3.113	3.064	2.666	3.153	2.985	0.594	0.705
	σ	1.210	1.103	1.165	1.527	1.143	1.096		
Extracurricular activities	\bar{x}	3.056	3.283	2.871	2.666	3.384	3.151	1.175	0.321
	σ	1.213	1.230	1.241	1.527	1.260	1.034		
Co-curricular activities	\bar{x}	2.981	3.283	2.833	2.000	3.307	2.985	1.535	0.178
	σ	1.166	1.214	1.221	1.000	1.250	1.160		
Industrial visits	\bar{x}	3.578	3.679	3.448	2.333	3.692	3.697	1.557	0.171
	σ	1.115	1.051	1.052	0.577	1.031	0.945		
Guest lectures	\bar{x}	3.597	3.566	3.487	3.000	3.692	3.633	0.431	0.827
	σ	1.091	1.047	1.016	1.000	0.751	0.979		
Tours	\bar{x}	3.195	3.358	3.217	3.333	3.538	3.323	0.445	0.817
	σ	1.187	1.039	1.191	0.577	1.050	1.091		
Safety and hygienic campus	\bar{x}	3.106	3.396	3.141	3.000	3.692	3.338	1.511	0.185
	σ	1.064	1.044	1.192	0.000	0.751	1.120		
Training and development support	\bar{x}	3.528	3.735	3.512	3.000	3.538	3.733	1.058	0.383
	σ	1.089	1.021	1.078	1.000	0.967	1.039		
The popularity of the college	\bar{x}	3.270	3.471	3.371	3.000	3.692	3.323	0.686	0.634
	σ	1.071	0.911	1.106	1.000	1.031	1.037		

Table 4: Occupation-wise results with regards to the perception of parents towards Predilection factors on choosing the colleges for their wards

Professional parents considered the major Predilection factors as Infrastructure, Experienced faculty members, Placement records, Industrial visits, Guest lecturing, educational tours, and Training and development. They are looking neutral for the strategies like location and proximity, existing students' strengths, Fees, safety, and hygiene factors. They have disagreement on Extracurricular aspects.

Agriculturist respondents disagreed with the factors of Infrastructure, Location, and proximity, experienced faculty members, student strength, placement records, transportation, fees, extra and co-curricular activities. They are even neutral on the factors of guest lecturing, safety and hygiene factors, Training and development, and the popularity of the Institution.

Household respondents agreed regarding Predilection factors such as location and proximity, experienced faculty members, existing students' strengths, placement records, transportation, and extra and co-curricular activities. They are even neutral on the factors of guest lecturing. They are neutral on the factors of infrastructure and fees.

Unorganized sector respondents agreed on the use of strategies by their service provider such as location and proximity, experienced faculty members, placement records,

Industrial visits, guest lecturing, sponsoring educational tours, safety and hygiene, training and development, and popularity of the institution. They are looking neutral for the factors of Infrastructure, existing students' strengths, Transportation, and extracurricular activities.

The ANOVA results indicate that the parents with different occupations are having a similar perception of predilection factors while choosing the colleges for their wards. Here we accept H_0 at a 5% level of significance.

Sr. No.	Customers Engagement Strategies	Overall Mean (\bar{x})	Overall Ranking
1	Placement Records	3.8315	1
2	Training and development	3.6112	2
3	Industrial visits	3.6000	3
4	Guest lectures	3.5843	4
5	Experienced faculty members	3.4764	5
6	The popularity of the Institution	3.3393	6
7	Educational tours	3.2697	7
8	Student's strength	3.2472	8
9	Location and proximity	3.2360	9
10	Safety and hygiene	3.2360	10
11	Infrastructure	3.1640	11
12	Extracurricular activities	3.0876	12
13	Transportation	3.0742	13
14	Cocurricular activities	2.7955	14
15	Fees Structure	2.7775	15

Table no 5-Overall Importance/Ranking given on Predilection factors in choosing the colleges for their wards

Overall Importance/Ranking given on Predilection factors on choosing the colleges for their wards

Ranking to the Predilection factors by the parents on choosing the colleges for their wards is done. As per the overall mean, placement records of the previous academic years have been found as the most important and preferred predilection factor. Training and development ranked second and therefore considered as the next important predilection factor. Industrial visits ranked third as per the overall mean and therefore, considered the third most important factor. Guest lecturer factor came fourth, followed by experienced faculty members which is assigned the fifth rank as per the response given by the respondents. Popularity ranked sixth, followed by educational tour programs which is assigned seven.

Existing students' strengths ranked eighth followed by proximity in ninth rank. Safety and hygiene are considered the next important factor by the respondents and assigned the tenth rank followed by infrastructure, which is assigned the eleventh rank as per the response given by customers. Extracurricular, transportation, and cocurricular ranked as the twelfth, thirteenth and fourteenth factors respectively. Surprisingly fee structure was considered the least important consideration. Overall, it is evident that Parents are quite much aware of various Predilection factors and do accept that most of these factors were considered by them while selecting the Institution for their wards.

V. FINDINGS

The gender profile of the respondents shows that 66:34 is a male and female ratio, and the results indicate significant differences in the perception of the male and female parent regarding the factors in choosing an institution for their wards except two predilection factors

The occupational profile shows that about eighteen percent are professional respondents and around twelve percent are a businessman. Very less respondents are from the category of agriculture and households. It is found that parents with different occupations got a similar opinion on Predilection factors in choosing the colleges for their wards.

While the respondents were assigned to rank the predilection factors, the first rank was given to the placement record of the institution, and the fee structure was considered the least ranked factor.

VI. CONCLUSION

Placement record, training & development, industrial visits, guest lecturer, and experienced faculty members, are the predilection factors that are ranked high by the parents. Institutions offering higher education may focus more on these factors. In many institutions, educational tours are not given much importance as it takes much time and efforts. Hence the educational institutions should concentrate more on educational tours. Extracurricular activities and cocurricular

activities are also considered as the least ranked factor. It was quite surprising to know that the fee structure and transportation were not considered as the main factors. This result shows that parents are ready to pay high fees and make their own transport arrangements when they find the institution is good for their ward's future.

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